

MODERN ENGLISH TEACHING METHODS

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Annotation. Language is a main tool of communication and it is confirmed as a connection of human being. However, communication does not include only speaking, but also listening that is the way to understand and feel how the conversation or relationships going on. According to statistics, almost billion people use English as a communicative language on a daily life and it has already entered to every field of the society. It has become a universal language and it shows that degree of requirements of learning English by people, no matter the youth, adults or senior is increasing dramatically. Especially, receptive skills are at the top of the list, therefore modern pedagogy has been facing various issues in the curriculum. This paper aims to clarify the importance of receptive skills as well as focus highly on some productive methods for teaching them in ESL and EFL classrooms.

Keywords: higher education, innovative methods, innovative technologies, educational process, cooperative learning, ICT, ELT.

Teaching is a complex activity that requires a teacher to use a set of integrated skills to inform the message to the students. A teacher must prepare many things before doing teaching activity, including materials, learning tools, and mentality in dealing with students. A teacher as a role player should know various way to achieve an effective teaching in classroom. That’s why teachers need strategies in teaching, including in teaching listening.

The definition of strategy in oxford dictionaries (2018) is a plan, method or series of maneuvers, plan of action that is designed to achieve a specific goal or result. While teaching strategies according to Gropper in Uno (2009) is the selection of certain types of exercises that in accordance with the teaching objectives to be achieved. So, teachers’ strategies are the different types or styles of plans that teachers use to achieve teaching learning goal. Teaching Strategy is a way of making decisions about a course, an individual class, or even an entire curriculum, beginning with an analysis of key variables in the teaching situation.

Listening is demanding process, not only because of the complexity of the process itself, but also due to factors that characterize the listener, the speaker, the content of the message, and any visual support that message. It means that listening is not as easy as many people think. Therefore, the thing that often happens toward the listening

teachers are that they find it difficult to adjust material with the student’s ability, they must challenge themselves to provide the material as creative as possible so that learners enthusiast and do not get bored because of the monotonous material. The next problem is inadequate learning media, the problems that often occur in listening laboratory because the equipment sometimes do not work properly.

The success of teaching is associated with certain factors such as strategies of material presentation, innovative, active and talented teachers and also good facilities. Teachers need to recognize and acknowledge the effective teaching, apply some teaching strategies, analyze the appropriate strategies and take action to modify teaching learning process to help students learn in a way that works for them. The difficulties in listening is a challenge for English teachers to provide and identify the appropriate strategies, which assess the effectiveness of the current 3 teaching style and consider innovative ways to improve the teaching to match students learning styles. Applying appropriate strategies of teaching may establish a better teaching and learning activity. Therefore, the researcher focuses to investigate “lecturers’ strategies: the use of media and material in teaching listening”.

Listening is one of the basic language skills which plays a significant role in daily communication and educational process. In daily communication, people usually spend around 45% of time in listening, 30% on speaking, 16% on reading, and only 9% on writing (Feyten, 1991). Unfortunately, listening comprehension is the most forgotten skill in second language acquisition. It is supposed that listening comprehension is a passive activity, but actually, it is an active process, the listeners must recognize the differences among sounds, understand vocabularies and the grammatical structures, get the meaning of language input and other prosodic proof from the text, and they must save the information in their mind to analyze the context in which the communication take place (Serri, 2012).

The modern effective methods of teaching listening skills include everything from interactive exercise to multimedia resources. Listening skills can best learn or improved through simple and engaging activities that focus more on the learning process instead of the final product. It doesn’t matter you are working with small or large groups of students, you can use any of the following technique to develop your own methods for teaching students how to listen well.

Interpersonal activities

The non-threatening and effective way for students to develop stronger listening skills can be done by interpersonal activities such as mock interviews and storytelling. Students are assigned to small groups of two or three they are given by a particular listening activity to complete. For instance, you may have an interview with a student for a job with a company or for an article in a newspaper. Even a storytelling activity

can give students the opportunity to ask one other question and then practice active listening skills.

Group activities

Large group activities also give the opportunity to the student to help through a helpful method for teaching listening skills to students. You can also begin with a simple group activity. For the first activity, students are divided into the groups of five or more and instruct them to learn one interest or hobby of at least two other group members. It is necessary to encourage students to ask clarifying questions during the activity and you may allow them to take notes because it is helpful. While, as time passes and their skills grow, you should limit students to only write notes after the completion of the first activity.

Audio segments

You can also teach listening skills to the students through audio segments such as radio programs, instructional lectures, online podcasts, and other audio messages. It is necessary to deploy interactive listening programs in class with students and then instruct them to repeat the exercise on their own. First of all, instruct students to prepare for listening by imagining anything they want to learn from the content of the audio segment. It's on you to choose shorter or longer audio segments and you can also choose more challenging or more accessible material for this type of exercise.

Video segments

The other most helpful resource for teaching listening skills is video segments that include short sketches, documentary films, dramatic or comedic material, news programs, and interview segments. As in the audio segment, you can select the portion and length of audio you can also do it in a video segment based on the skill level of your students. First, watch the segment without any sound and discuss it together with the student. Encourage your student what they think will be the content of the segment. This will improve their listening and thinking power.

In conclusion, based on the research by using library research, researcher can conclude that dictation is very suitable to teach listening to the students. It can also give benefits for the students, such as increasing their confidence and motivation, increasing their pronunciation, and improving their listening skills. With the existence of dictation, students can improve their abilities, especially their listening skills. By using dictation, the teacher can teach listening to the students efficiently, so that the learning objectives can be achieved.

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